

Table S7 Gene expression analysis for putative functional SNPs using 1,006 breast tumor samples in TCGA

SNP ID	Gene	Effect Allele	Ref Allele	Beta ^a	P-value
Signal 1					
rs812020	<i>PTHLH</i>	A	C	0.03	0.65
rs812020	<i>CCDC91</i>	A	C	0.06	0.27
Signal 2					
rs788463	<i>PTHLH</i>	A	T	0.04	0.69
rs10843066	<i>PTHLH</i>	T	C	0.07	0.41
rs788463	<i>CCDC91</i>	A	T	0.01	0.88
rs10843066	<i>CCDC91</i>	T	C	0.03	0.70
Signal 3					
rs10843110	<i>PTHLH</i>	T	G	0.13	0.02
rs56318627	<i>PTHLH</i>	C	T	0.15	0.01
rs11049453	<i>PTHLH</i>	G	A	0.15	0.01
rs10843110	<i>CCDC91</i>	T	G	-0.11	0.08
rs56318627	<i>CCDC91</i>	C	T	-0.11	0.07
rs11049453	<i>CCDC91</i>	G	A	-0.13	0.03

^a The regression coefficient for each SNP estimated in the residual linear regression.